

THE SOCIAL NECESSITY AND PRACTICAL STATUS OF LEARNING INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH AND IMPLEMENTING THEM INTO THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS (PIRLS)

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Abstract. *This article discusses modern methods and tools for improving the mechanisms of using international assessment programs to increase the effectiveness of education in primary grades, and the use of innovative technologies aimed at developing reading comprehension skills in preparation for the PIRLS international study.*

Keywords: *educational effectiveness, international research, PIRLS, innovative technologies, professional development, parental example, personal example.*

INTRODUCTION. Today, the world community has seriously begun to address the issue of improving the quality and efficiency of education, and successful results can be seen in the education systems of leading Western countries. The main indicator of the quality of education is the result of the learner. Knowledge is directly related to reading skills, and the formation of reading and comprehension skills and competencies in the educational process is one of the important tasks. Reading is an important skill that is the basis for learning and personal development. Good reading is a necessary skill not only for academic success, but also for finding one's place in life. A number of works have been carried out in the field of education based on the seven priority areas outlined in the Decree No. PF-60 "On the Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026".

Based on the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to organize international studies in the field of assessing the quality of education in the public education system" No. 997 dated 08.12.2018, the introduction of international studies PIRLS, TIMSS, PISA, TALIS, EGRA, EGMA in Uzbekistan (preparation for the second cycle) was determined. In order to introduce these studies, preparations for the next cycle of international studies are being carried out step by step based on the roadmap of the National Center for International Studies on the Assessment of the Quality of Education under the State Inspectorate for Supervision of Education Quality. These international assessment programs and studies within their framework are organized by the International Association for the Assessment of Educational Achievements of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development on a periodic basis in cooperation with countries of the world.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's assessment of education as the third renaissance and the focus on education as the main direction of the Development Strategy are important processes. In particular, the adoption of a new National Curriculum and the development of textbooks with a new vision and appearance that align with international research assessment programs are clear evidence of changes in the quality of education. According to paragraph 34 of Appendix 2 of Decree No. PF-134 of May 11, 2022 "On

Approval of the National Program for the Development of Public Education for 2022-2026", we would not be wrong if we say that increasing the number of regular readers in secondary schools has become an incentive to arouse and increase interest in reading and books among students.

The development of a positive attitude towards reading and reading in a person does not happen by itself. For this, it is necessary to introduce each person to books, starting from preschool age, and create the necessary pedagogical conditions for them to understand their importance and practical value in society and human life. In introducing a person to books, the first stage of continuous education, which is carried out in a consistent, systematic, and purposeful manner, is the open-ended classes. The establishment of systematic activities in them based on organizational, methodological, pedagogical, and psychological requirements allows the development of reading skills in primary school students.

In order to increase the effectiveness of education, it is important to form and develop students' skills in working with text, reading comprehension, and improving their reading culture in the lessons of "Mother Language and Reading Literacy". In this regard, the priority task is to develop methodologies for improving students' literacy, developing skills in analysis, synthesis, and comparison when working with text, conducting research on the experience and problems of using advanced methods of the PIRLS international study in assessing educational outcomes, and increasing educational efficiency using the recommended handbooks and workbooks.

The PIRLS study reported that in the process of completing tasks aimed at assessing reading comprehension, finding clearly presented information is considered an important factor, accounting for 20%, drawing direct conclusions for 30%, summarizing, interpreting, and integrating ideas and information for 30%, and evaluating and critically approaching content and text elements for 20%. [1]

Uzbek research scientists Rakhmonova D., Ergasheva S.R., Turdiyev S. R., Shodmonova A.Sh., Nishonboyeva M., Turayeva Z., and others are conducting research on the experience and problems of using advanced PIRLS methods in assessing educational outcomes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. Students' skills in summarizing, interpreting, and synthesizing ideas and information (30% through PIRLS XT texts), evaluating content and text elements, and approaching them critically (20%) are formed and developed through the development of their creative abilities [2]. Given the relatively low percentage of students completing the tasks mentioned above (PIRLS 2021), it is important to form and develop creative abilities in our students; to teach them to evaluate content and text elements, and to form and develop a critical approach (PIRLS 2026). A person's creativity is manifested in their thinking, communication, emotions, and specific types of activities. Using a variety of methods and techniques to develop creativity and reveal a child's unique potential and talent in the educational process can not only increase educational efficiency, but also enhance the child's intelligence, worldview, especially in primary school students, and instill a sense of confidence in themselves and their future in the world around them. The use of several methods, including brainstorming, puzzles, assessments, concept maps, and problem situations, is effective in introducing creativity into the educational process. At the same time, it also creates the opportunity for creative and broad thinking and serves to demonstrate that a child has some abilities.

In the PIRLS 2021 study, students from Uzbekistan participated for the first time and took 49th place among 57 countries. Uzbek students scored 437 points out of 500, the international average. When the study authors divided the results into 4 groups according to the level of reading

skills (low level - 400 points, average - 475 points, high - 550 points and advanced - 625), 70% of Uzbek students recorded low and 34% average results, 7% of students achieved high results, and there were no students who achieved advanced levels. [3]

When comparing text types (informational text and fiction text), it was noted that Uzbek students understood fiction text relatively better than informational text: the average score for understanding fiction text was 438, while for informational text this indicator was 434.

When compared in terms of reading skills, Uzbek students scored higher (441 points) on the skills of finding and interpreting explicit information. They scored significantly lower (430 points) on the skills of interpreting, integrating (combining information) and evaluating, which are considered relatively higher-level skills. [4]

The study found that students' socioeconomic background affects their academic performance. In Uzbekistan, there is a significant gap between the performance of children from families with high, average and low socioeconomic status. It also found that students in schools with a higher proportion of children from wealthier families performed relatively better.

The impact of family socioeconomic background on student academic performance: comparing the performance of children from families with different socioeconomic statuses with the average score for Uzbekistan.

According to the study, parents' attitudes toward reading also influenced students' results. In Uzbekistan, children of parents who "like reading a lot" scored an average of 449 points, children of those who "read books" scored 431 points, and children of families who "do not like reading" scored 401 points.

The study also found that students who had basic reading skills before starting school performed better by the end of grade 4 than students who did not know how to read or write before starting school. For example, in Uzbekistan, the difference in scores between students who were good readers before school and those who did not know how to read before school was 36 points.

The study also found that school resources, discipline and safety also affect student performance. 49% of Uzbek students in the study studied were in schools with some level of resource shortages, and 35% studied in schools with moderate or severe discipline problems. For reference, the study included students from Uzbekistan who entered grade 1 in 2016. A previous study by UNICEF showed that more than half of grade 4 students did not understand the text they read.

Will Uzbekistan participate in the sixth cycle of the international PIRLS survey (PIRLS 2026)? To date, according to information from the IEA official website, the number of countries

and education systems that have expressed interest in participating in the PIRLS 2026 survey is 61. Uzbekistan is also on this list.

Countries and education systems interested in participating in PIRLS 2026

How are preparations being made for this process? How prepared are 4th grade students from Uzbekistan for the international survey to be held in April of the 2025-2026 academic year?

It is important to assess reading literacy at a social and cultural level within a given class. Because a student's academic literacy manifests itself in 3 different ways: 1) operational literacy - this is knowledge of the language; 2) cultural and intercultural literacy - understanding speech, culture, and a specific environment (for example, the use of language, the use of the language of a group of people or a region, for example, information technology, medical terms, etc.); 3) critical literacy - a deeper understanding of how knowledge is formed and transformed (for example, reading literacy includes many elements such as critical thinking, decoding, and comprehension, and also performs a number of important functions in social terms. Their implementation is influenced by intrapsychic (internal psychic), interpersonal and environmental factors. There are some difficulties and obstacles that can hinder the development of academic reading literacy, including social background, learning disabilities, level of upbringing, environmental factors, unstable family environment, problems in education (poor quality of education), distracting factors and other factors.

To achieve the level of literacy in the three aspects listed above, it is important to first teach children to read works of art and informational texts with explanation. One of the methods close to the explanatory reading of a work of art is creative reading. The outstanding methodologist scientist N.I. Kudryashov includes the following work methods in the creative reading method: a) a speech by teachers aimed at the interpretation of the literary text and ensuring the correct and as deep as possible, emotional perception of the work by students; b) a conversation aimed at deepening the direct impressions of students from the read work and directing their attention to the important ideological and artistic features of the text, or posing an artistic, moral, socio-political problem arising from the read work; c) a speech by the teacher aimed at the use of the artistic experiences of students after reading the work in the process of studying the work. One of the methods close to the explanatory reading of a work of art is creative reading. The outstanding methodologist scientist N.I. Kudryashov includes the following work methods in the creative

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It can be useful in raising the quality of education in Uzbekistan to international standards, reforming the national education system, and creating programs to improve the content of education, training and advanced training of teaching staff. [5] In the process of preparing primary school students for the international PIRLS study, it is important to analyze the development of students' logical and creative thinking skills through texts, and to interpret and explain the words and their meanings in the text, as well as to apply innovative methods in practice. It is based on focusing on the ability of students to create their own interpretation of a literary text by reading it, taking into account their age and psychological characteristics, individual capabilities, and developing their breadth of imagination and creative thinking. In addition, the IEA organization (16.05.2023) can use the research materials for the training of pedagogical personnel for primary grades of secondary schools, as well as for the creation of methodological manuals for pedagogical staff working in the field, and to improve their knowledge in the field of pedagogical and methodological issues.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, it can be said that while participation in the 2021 PIRLS international study is considered a first step for Uzbek students, it is advisable to prepare students for this international study in stages over the next five years, that is, from the literacy period (in primary education) until the end of the 4th quarter of the 4th grade.

The process of adequately preparing for the PIRLS 2026 international study is considered to be aimed at increasing the reading culture not only during lessons and club activities at school, during visits to classroom, school and city (district) school libraries, but also in the family. To this end, it is necessary to establish "Parental Reading Culture" centers under the jurisdiction of city and district Public Education Departments, and "Family Reading Houses" based on national libraries; national librarians in cities and districts, in cooperation with schools (a special higher education employee must work at the expense of the state unit) and the neighborhood (a special employee must work at the expense of the state unit), organize training sessions and debates for parents. There is no doubt that the organic and consistent collaboration with teachers, primary school students, and their parents over the next five years, i.e. between 2022 and 2026, will yield positive results.

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